

PHYTO-COMPOUNDS REPLACING THE SYNTHETIC COMPOUNDS IN SKINCARE INDUSTRIES: A SYTEMATIC REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Skin is the most vulnerable organ of human body that is exposed to different types of environmental conditions. It protects the human body by acting as physical barrier. Since it is the first line of defence many pathogens, chemicals, pollution and radiation can affect the integrity of its three layers. To prevent and cure skin issues there are various products and technologies available in the market. Skin care products are the topical applications that are for external use. These are targeted to enhance the texture and appearance of skin. The medicinal ingredients used in the formulations can protect and can treat skin diseases as well. Redness, itchiness, inflammation and allergies are some symptoms of unhealthy skin. There is a need of sustainable natural alternatives to these chemical raw materials so as to stop the harm being caused to the environment. The consumers are also becoming aware of the

side effects of these synthetic products and demanding for the organic and herbal products. This review reveals the potent bioactive compounds from plants and techniques to extract them. Plant- based ingredients represent a potent alternative to chemicals used in skincare products. The moisturizing, anti-aging, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, photoprotective and anti-cancer properties of various phytoextracts have been proven. Spinach, blue pea, peanut and soya bean are becoming popular in beauty industry for their promising effects on skin.

KEYWORDS: Skin, Skin Diseases, Cosmetic, Skincare Products, Phytocompounds, Synthetic Compounds.

1. INTRODUCTION

Skin is the largest organ of animal body that is exposed to external environment. It acts a physical barrier against any trauma, pressure, infection, pollution, radiation, etc. It also functions to sense and regulate the optimum conditions in animals.^[1] Human skin is vulnerable to various skin diseases. Medicinal preparations have been in use since so long to prevent and treat skin disorders. Such preparations are termed as skincare products. The personal care products represent the largest category in the beauty industry.^[2] Earlier these preparations were solely herbal in nature but as this skincare practice has been industrialized, synthetic chemicals have become a core part of the formulations that are targeted towards enhancing the texture, appearance and tone of skin. Chemical-based skincare and cosmetic products can cause serious side effects on human health and environment that are being addressed by the researchers as well as the consumers.^[3] In the recent years, the demand for natural and herbal products has been increased in both developed and developing countries, due to the awareness of the effects of synthetic products. The exploitation of natural resources like phytochemicals, essential oils, etc. represents a high potential for sustainable development of skincare industries. Researches are being carried on discovering potent plant materials and developing efficient technology to incorporate the plant-based ingredients in the skincare and cosmetic products.^[4]

Skin also contributes in insulation, vitamin D secretion, homeostasis, UV protection, etc. Various immune cells like; B-cells, T-cells, macrophages, monocytes are found in skin that, respond to potential damage or infection. Though hair and nails are not a part of skin layer, they share common structural components. They develop from epidermal cells. Hair perform protection, insulation and sensory functions. Nails protect tips of the fingers and toes. The three layers, viz. epidermis, dermis and hypodermis form the skin. The epidermis is the outermost layer that acts as initial block to any damage. Dermis the middle layer consists of connective tissues, lymphatic vessels, blood vessels, sweat gland and hair follicles. Hypodermis, the deepest layer mainly contains fat. Damage to any one layer of skin may spread to other layers and sub-layers.^[5]

The human skin renews by itself in every 28 days. The skin of an adult weighs approximately 8-15 pounds. Generally, the pH of skin lies in the range of 4.7 to 5.7. The sweat glands present in the skin layers can produce up to 3 liters of sweat per day. Human skin can host more than thousands of bacterial species as normal flora.^[6]

Factors affecting skin health

The characteristics of skin vary depending on the location and function; e.g. skin thickness. Thinnest skin is found over eyelids while back and buttocks have comparatively thick layer of skin. Face is the most exposed area of skin that is most susceptible to sun damage and pollution. The extreme environmental conditions like exposure to UV radiation, pollution and other intrinsic factors including aging, smoking and other toxic habits may contribute in the depletion of skin layers leading to the pigmentation, wrinkles and other skin diseases. This can even result in skin cancer. Damage to skin may result into skin disorders that are marked by rashes, inflammation, itching and other skin changes. Some skin diseases can be hereditary or can be due to person's lifestyle. There can be different skin diseases like; acne, eczema (Atopic dermatitis), psoriasis, ichthyosis, shingles, hives, vitiligo, etc.

External as well as internal factors are responsible for the long-term fate of the skin. Different environmental conditions have different effects on the appearance of skin. The skin health primarily depends on the hereditary. Lifestyle habits also have a serious impact on the human skin. The external factors that affect skin health can be climatic conditions (e.g. humidity, extreme temperature, etc.), sun exposure, pollution, air quality, etc. On the other hand hereditary, hormones and age also play an important role as internal factors in deciding the skin quality and appearance. Along with these, the skin also depends on the lifestyle of a human. Mental health, diet, adequate sleep and other habits also play a significant role in the maintenance of the skin health.

Some factors that contribute in deterioration of skin layers are as follows:

- i) **Pollution:** Pollutants like particulate matter, nitrogen dioxide, soot, etc. enter the skin layers through pores and lead to degradation of collagen.
- ii) **UV radiation:** Excessive exposure to sunlight results in photo-aging that involves formation of abnormal elastin and fastens the breakdown of collagen. Skin damaged by sun loses its flexibility.
- iii) **Lifestyle:** Personal habits like diet, repeated facial expressions, dehydration, smoking, lack of sleep, unhealthy skin care routine, etc. speed up the skin aging process.
- iv) **Hereditary:** The genes that inherit from parents to their next generation play an important role in determining the quality and ability of skin cells production and related proteins, thereby contribute in the development of a healthy skin.^[7]

Human skin especially; facial skin is mostly prone to deformation and hence precautions must be taken to avoid underlying damages. Here are some preventive methods:

- i) Protection from sun damage
- ii) Healthy skin care routine
- iii) Cleaning and moisturizing
- iv) Adequate amount of water intake
- v) Balanced diet
- vi) Avoiding toxic habits.

Skin issues can be cured by targeting the root cause of the disorder and if treated on time. Various treatment options are their like home-made remedies, topical applications, dermatological consults, etc. Aging is a part of life; it doesn't need to be treated until it makes someone feel uncomfortable and conscious about how a person looks. If it bothers someone then one can go for some available treatment options to make them less visible, like anti-aging creams, laser skin resurfacing, medicines, fillers, facelift, etc. Any artificial treatment has potential to cause adverse side effects; also some complications may arise so it's better to consult a dermatologist before starting a treatment. Side effects may involve swelling, redness, allergic reactions, acne, pigmentation, pain, etc.

Skincare products

Skin care is the practice of improving skin appearance, maintaining skin health and treating skin disorders. It involves a variety of products, activities and lifestyle choices targeting skin nourishment, cleansing, treatment and protection. A good skincare practice can help to improve skin health with by preventing skin issues like dryness, early aging, acne, pigmentation, etc. Skin care formulation involves mixing ingredients in defined proportions to form a product that is effective, safe and tailored to the demands of consumers. For designing any beauty product, understanding the interaction between different ingredients and desired effects is crucial.

Aspects of skincare formulations

- **Selection of ingredients:** The selection of ingredients is based on the desired final effect of product; e.g. moisturizing, anti-inflammatory, anti-aging, brightening, etc. The

compatibility of one ingredient with other must also be considered while making a beauty product.

- **Proportion and order:** The effectiveness, texture and stability of a skincare product depend on the proportion of the ingredients used and also the order of their mixing is crucial for a successful product.
- **Stability and shelf-life:** Stabilizers and preservatives are incorporated in the formulations in order to make them stable and efficient for a long period of time. A preservative helps to prevent any microbial growth in the product and stabilizer enhances the integrity of all the components used.
- **Safety:** A beauty product must be safe to use on skin and align with the relevant regulations.
- **Testing:** The testing and evaluation of the formulation is necessary to ensure its efficacy, safety and stability.

Types of skin care formulations

Different formulations have different forms; some can have water-like consistency, others may be runny like honey, some can be solid bars or sticks and semi-solid, gel or creams. The viscosity the whole formulation defines the form of a product. Emulsification is a process that is used to mix the ingredients that usually mix with each other (e.g. oil and water) to make a smooth mixture. It stabilizes the product formulation and prevents the separation of ingredients. The mixture formed by this process is termed as emulsion that consists of two immiscible phases. Spontaneously formed micro-emulsions are generally stable, otherwise all are not stable. A simple formulation may contain an aqueous phase, an oil phase and an emulsifying agent. Emulsions may vary in size and type of the two phases. The two categories of emulsions on the basis of quantity of two phases; here water and oil, can be: Oil-in-water (O/W) **and** Water-in-oil (W/O).

O/W emulsions have oil drops immersed in aqueous phase while W/O emulsions are formed of water drops immersed in oil phase. O/W emulsions are the most commonly used as they are suitable to create creams and body lotions for all types of skin. On the other hand, W/O emulsions are formed to target dryness related skin issues. Also O/W emulsions are readily absorbed as compared to W/O type.

Creams: Creams are semi-solid in texture and used as topical applications. They can be either O/W or W/O. As mentioned above, O/W emulsions are lighter to absorb. Creams are used as topical application to treat various skin disorders, dryness, inflammation, beautifying, etc.

Lotions: Lotions are generally less viscous than creams. It is due to high amount of aqueous phase. They are easily absorbed. These are lighter version of moisturizing creams.^[8]

Table 1.1: Types of skin care formulations.

S. No.	Formulation type	Effect
1	Moisturizers and lotions	Protection and hydration
2	Cleansers	Dirt and impurity removal
3	Serums	Targets specific skin issues
4	Sunscreen	Protection from harmful UV rays

Effects of synthetic ingredients used in cosmetic industries

To improve the skin texture, appearance and quality different ingredients (with potent skincare properties like moisturizing, cleansing, nurturing, replenishing, etc.) are combined to finalize a skin care product. But along with the effective results of such skincare products, there are growing concerns over the potential harm caused by synthetic chemicals used for the preparation, such as parabens, phthalates, artificial fragrances and petrochemicals, which have been linked to skin irritation, allergic responses, permanent endocrine disruption and long-term health risks.^[9]

Not only health concerns, chemical-based ingredients in skincare products have raised environmental concerns too. The manufacturing process of synthetic chemicals used in the skincare industry, may release pollutants as by-product that are non-biodegradable and require high energy input. The washed off product by consumers, runs down into the water system highly impacts the nature and its balance.^[10] The unorganized disposal of such chemicals, enter into the water bodies which results into the loss of sunlight absorption ability of aquatic species due to sunrays blocking components. This can also result in the reduced fertility of soil.^[11] All these events might result into the long-term harmful effects on the nature like bioaccumulation of the heavy materials, squalene, nano-particles etc. in the species of different trophic levels. Additionally, the consumer shift towards natural skincare is fueled by a growing understanding of the toxicological profiles of common chemical ingredients. As consumers become more educated, they demand safer, more sustainable

alternatives that not only protect their skin but also support their health and the environment.^[12]

Developing naturally derived alternatives that are more effective in resolving the skin related problems with no side effects with reduced environmental contamination can be a solution to this. Natural ingredients have been used since so long to treat skin diseases and injuries. Such ingredients can be easily obtained from plants and microorganisms around us. Replacing the chemicals used in cosmetic industries with renewable ingredients will lead to sustainable production of the beauty products. Also developing a technology that ensures the use of waste produced during the manufacturing process of the product will minimize the pollution caused by cosmetic industries. This is need of the hour that the synthetic products whether in cosmetic industry or any other industry must be replaced by organic products that will likely to have least or no effect on the ecosystem thereby contributing in the development of a sustainable environment.

Plants in cosmetic industry

The incorporation of plants as main raw material has been remarkably increased due to their safe application. The beneficial natural compounds have a wide range of application in the field of medicine, food, agricultural and cosmetic industry.^[13] Extracts of most of the plants have shown antimicrobial properties against disease causing bacteria. It has been reported that bioactive compounds found in plants have potential to treat so many human diseases without any side effects.

Recently, an increased interest in the cosmeceuticals and dermocosmetics produced from botanical ingredients has been observed. Cosmetic formulations are being incorporated with the botanicals that have anti-inflammatory, soothing, skin-barrier, moisturizing and antioxidant properties that support healthy skin. Plant extracts are recommended as they are potent agents to treat skin disorders as well as dry and mature skin because they act to maintain the integrity of skin's structure. Plant extracts are a rich source of bioactive components of plants that have significant effect on human skin. Certain bioactive compounds obtained from plants may have both medicinal (to treat skin disorders) and skin care properties (antibacterial, hydrating, smoothening, lightening, antioxidant, cleansing or regenerating).^[14]

Table 1.2: Plants in cosmetic industries.

S. No.	Plant source	Target	Effect
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1	Aloe (<i>Aloe vera</i>)	Skin /Hair	Moisturizes, reduces skin spots
2.	Coconut (<i>Cocos nucifera</i>)	Skin	Antiseptic properties, Photoprotective
3.	Papaya (<i>Carica papaya</i>)	Skin	Anti-aging, anti-oxidant, anti-inflammatory
4.	Rice (<i>Oryza sp.</i>)	Skin	UV protection, anti-aging
5.	Soya (<i>Glycine max</i>)	Skin	Anti-inflammatory, de-pigmentation, antioxidant
6.	Blue pea (<i>Clitoria ternatea</i>)	Skin	Anti-aging, anti-inflammatory,
7.	Peanuts (<i>Arachis hypogaea</i>)	Skin	Anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, anticancer
8.	Spinach (<i>Spinacia oleracea</i>)	Skin	Hydration, photo-protection, anti-carcinogenic

Advantages of plant-based ingredients

Plant-based ingredients provide multiple advantages over their synthetic counterparts. They are inherently biocompatible, which means they are less likely to irritate or damage the skin. These ingredients are also biodegradable, which significantly reduces their environmental impact compared to petrochemical-derived compounds. Furthermore, plants are a renewable resource, and the cultivation of plant-based ingredients can be integrated into sustainable agricultural practices. This provides an opportunity to reduce dependency on petrochemicals, promoting a circular economy where natural resources are replenished rather than depleted.

Notably, natural ingredients, those found in plants like spinach, peanut, soybean, blue pea, etc. are rich in bioactive compounds that offer targeted skin benefits like anti-aging, hydration, anti-inflammatory effects, and protection from UV damage.

Phytochemicals

Biologically active compounds of plants or phytochemicals are categorized as Primary and Secondary metabolites. Primary active compounds are synthesized by plants for their basic requirements i.e. structure building and as energy source which include sugars, fats, proteins, enzymes, amino acids, purines, pyrimidines, chlorophyll, etc. On the other hand, Secondary metabolites are produced by plants in response environmental conditions and are not directly involved in their growth and development. But these play significant role in the interaction of plants with their environmental conditions in order to be more competitive under extreme conditions. Some examples are terpenes, steroids, alkaloids, saponins, tannins, resins, volatile

oils, phenolics, etc.^[15] Following are the type of phytochemicals that are generally found in different plant parts -

- a. **Phenolic compounds** are widely distributed and represent largest category of phytochemicals. They play protective roles in plants and have several beneficial roles in humans due to their anti-oxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-allergic, anti-carcinogenic, antihypertensive and cardioprotective properties.
- b. **Tannins** are commonly found in fruits, legumes, grasses, etc. These are involved in the defensive responses against predators and UV rays in plants. Due to their high level of biological activity they are widely used in pharmaceuticals, nutraceuticals and food industry. They exhibit anti-allergic, anti-oxidant, anti-cancer and anti-microbial properties
- c. **Alkaloids** play an important role in plants in protection against disease causing microbes, insects and herbivores. They are antibacterial and antifungal in nature. Earlier they were used as dyes and poison but with developing scientific researches it was discovered that alkaloids have pharmacological properties like anti-hypersensitivity, anti-arrhythmic effect, anti-malarial (quinine), anti-cancer and some can be used analgesic.
- d. **Terpenoids** are naturally occurring lipids, found in almost all living organisms and hence comprise largest category of secondary metabolites. They are found as main constituents in plants' essential oil. Commercially they are used as flavors and fragrance in foods and cosmetics.
- e. **Saponins** are named so because of their ability to form foam in aqueous solution. Most of them are known to protect plants from moulds and insects. In animals they may act as anti-fungal and anti-viral agents. Moreover, they exhibit anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant, anti-carcinogenic, immunity boosting and cholesterol-lowering properties.^[16]

Phytoextracts

Nowadays, extracts from different plant parts are being used in cosmetics as potent ingredients. Phytoextracts are a mixture of compounds that act as multipotent ingredients. Natural compounds from plants can be used as anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, photoprotective, regenerative, wound-healing, de-pigmenting, anti-aging and coloring agents. Preventing or reversing skin-aging is a great challenge, hence treating it at the level of epidermis, dermis and subcutaneous tissues is considered. Phytochemicals are found in all parts of plant, but their types and concentration may vary depending upon the plant species, environmental conditions and growth stage.^[17]

Table 1.3: Phytochemicals and their properties.

S.No.	Phytochemicals	Plant parts	Properties
1.	Saponins	Leaves, roots and stem	Anticancer, anti-inflammatory, anti-viral, anti-microbial
2.	Flavonoids (polyphenol)	Leaves and fruits	Anti-oxidant, anti-tumor, anti-bacterial
3.	Tannins	Bark, roots and leaves	Anti-carcinogenic, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial
4.	Terpenoids	Flowers, fruits, leaves and stem	Anti-cancer, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant
5.	Alkaloids	Leaves, roots and stem	Analgesic, anti-microbial antiinflammatory, antimicrobial

Fig. 1.1: Basic structures of phytochemicals.

To use botanical compounds a thorough understanding of the components that contribute in constructing the whole skin structure and texture is necessary, based on which potent ingredients can be picked for the formulation. Impact of aging on skin may include; imbalance in the distribution of natural moisturizing agents, reduced amounts of lipids (mainly ceramides), oxidation of intracellular lipids leading to dryness, reduced collagen synthesis, low hyaluronic acid, disrupted elastin fibres, etc. Reduced activity of fibroblasts highly contributes to skin aging as these are the cells that synthesize collagen fibres. Resistance to stretching and reduced skin resilience with inadequate moisture marks skin-aging.^[18]

Here are some plant resources that can be used as potent ingredient to formulate an effective and eco-friendly skin care product-

A. Spinach (*Spinacia oleracea*): It belongs to Chenopodiaceae family. It is a leafy green flowering plant. It has been used as a nutritious vegetable for centuries due to its rich nutrient profile. It caught attention in the cosmetic industries because of the growing trend of incorporating plant-based organic ingredients in the skin care products. It is popular for its skin conditioning properties that have been discovered recently. Spinach is rich in minerals, antioxidants and vitamins like vitamin A, C, E and K. The presence of **vitamin C** makes it an effective ingredient in collagen synthesis, helping to promote **skin firmness** and **elasticity**. Its strong **antioxidant** properties help to **neutralize free radicals** and prevent **skin aging**.^[19] Spinach also has anti-inflammatory properties that aid in **detoxifying** and **soothing** the skin.^[20] Additionally, spinach is known to have a **UV-protective effect**, reducing the harmful impacts of sunlight exposure. It also contains flavonoids, carotenoids, iron, calcium and folate. These components are responsible for its nourishing and rejuvenating effects on the skin. It can be a potent ingredient for a skin care product.^[21]

B. Peanut (*Arachis hypogaea*): It is also known as groundnut and belongs to legumes family. Peanut is used as a good source of protein in diet. It can be consumed in the form of butter and oil as well. Peanuts contain significant levels of **resveratrol**, an antioxidant polyphenol known for its **anti-aging** and **anti-inflammatory properties**. Resveratrol has been found to inhibit the breakdown of **collagen**, helping to maintain **skin structure** and reduce the formation of wrinkles. Peanuts are also rich in **monounsaturated fatty acids** (like oleic acid), which act as emollients, providing hydration and improving the **skin barrier function**. **Vitamin E** in peanuts further promotes skin regeneration by fighting oxidative stress and **repairing damaged skin cells**. Peanut oil is a potent ingredient in cosmetic industries as it acts as a moisturizing agent. It readily absorbs in the skin layers leaving them hydrated. Also the skin of peanut has antioxidant properties that make it more valuable in beauty industry. It is rich in niacin (vitamin B) too.^[22]

C. Soya beans (*Glycine soja*): It is a leguminous plant that contains bioactive components like phenolic acids, flavonoids, isoflavonoids and tannins. Isoflavones, like **genistein** and **daidzein**, are phytoestrogens that mimic the effect of estrogen in the body. These compounds stimulate **collagen production**, improve **skin elasticity**, and help in **reducing the appearance of fine lines** and **wrinkles**. Soy also contains **lecithin**, an

emulsifier that helps to maintain the skin's natural moisture. Moreover, **saponin** present in it, has anti-inflammatory and **skin-soothing properties**, which can help reduce skin irritation and redness. Soja oil is rich in fatty acids like oleic acid, palmitic acid, linoleic acid, stearic acid, etc. It is a cost-effective ingredient offering notable results/outcomes.^[23]

D. Blue pea (*Clitoria ternatea*): Blue pea, also known as **butterfly pea**, is a vibrant blue flower plant. It is rich in antioxidant, flavonoids, peptides, etc. It is used in a variety of fancy cocktails and teas. It is getting popular in skin care industries due to its exceptional anti-aging properties. It contains **anthocyanins**—a class of flavonoids which has powerful antioxidant and **anti-inflammatory** properties. These compounds provide protection to the skin from oxidative stress and **sun damage**. Blue pea also contains **phenolic acids** that inhibit **glycation** — a process that accelerates **skin aging**. The **skin brightening** property of blue pea makes it a valuable ingredient in formulations designed to promote an even skin tone and **reduce hyperpigmentation**. It has numerous skin care benefits as mentioned below:

- Prevents premature aging
- Soothing and calming Skin.^[24]

Table 1.4: Plants and their role in skin care.

Plant Source	Key Bioactive Compounds	Skincare Benefits
Spinach	Vitamins A, C, E, flavonoids, carotenoids	Antioxidant, UV protection, anti-aging, skin renewal
Peanut	Resveratrol, vitamin E, oleic acid, linoleic acid	Moisturizing, anti-wrinkle, skin barrier repair
Soybean	Isoflavones (genistein, daidzein), lecithin	Collagen stimulation, skin elasticity, depigmentation
Blue Pea Flower	Anthocyanins, flavonoids, phenolic acids	Skin brightening, anti-glycation, antioxidant protection

Current research and applications

While the potential of these plants is widely recognized, scientific research on their application in skincare is still in its early stages. Several studies have elaborated the efficacy of spinach-based antioxidants in protecting against UV-induced skin damage. Likewise, peanut-derived resveratrol has shown promising improvement in skin texture and reduction in wrinkles in clinical trials. However, the bioavailability and formulation challenges—such as the stability and efficiency of active compounds in skincare products—still need to be fixed. Current researches are focused on improving the extraction methods, enhancing compound delivery, and optimizing formulations for maximum efficacy.

Future scope and innovation

The future of skincare lies in green cosmetics that can be achieved by advancing extraction technologies, such as supercritical fluid extraction and nanotechnology, to enhance the yield and bioavailability of bioactive compounds. Furthermore, development of other technologies, to increase the efficiency of the potent natural ingredients can be carried out, to completely utilize the bioactive properties of the ingredients. For example, nanocarriers can be used to encapsulate compounds or nanoemulsions from spinach, peanut, soybean, and blue pea can be produced to improve their penetration into the skin. Additionally, synergistic formulations—combining multiple plant extracts—could be explored to achieve greater efficacy in relieving various skin concerns. Nowadays, there is a growing trend of artificial intelligence in every sector, so cosmetic industries can face a revolutionary change by using AI-based ingredients matching for a particular skin type. By incorporating plant-based ingredients in the formulation, rural agricultural economy can also be supported. As the skincare industries move towards sustainability, research is also needed to ensure that the plant ingredients are sourced responsibly, with an emphasis on organic farming and fair trade practices. The development of green chemistry techniques for extraction, coupled with eco-friendly packaging, could further assure the sustainability aspect of the natural skincare products.

CONCLUSION

The results of skincare products undoubtedly boost confidence and appearance of a person, but there are unsaid consequences on human health and environment. Several studies have proved the associated side effects of the chemicals used in beauty products. Hence, the shift from synthetic to natural ingredients in skincare products presents an exciting opportunity for both consumers and the environment. By incorporating bioactive compounds from plants like spinach, peanut, soybean, and blue pea, skincare products can offer effective, sustainable, and safe alternatives to synthetic formulations. However, further research is needed to optimize the extraction processes, increase the yield of bioactive compounds, enhance the efficiency of final formulation, improve product stability, and explore the full potential of these bioactive compounds in order to treat skin aging, inflammation, UV damage and other skin issues. As the demand for risk-free, natural and eco-friendly skincare products continues to rise, the role of biologically active plant compounds will play decisive role in shaping the future of the cosmetics industry. Therefore, it is necessary to find a balance between beauty and health, so

that in achieving the exterior attractiveness one should not have to compromise his/her inter well-being.

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